

Impact of Ownership Structure on Firm Performance: Moderating Role of Tax Avoidance. Evidence From Non-Financial Listed Firms of Pakistan

Sabah Younus, M.Wasim Rana, Ume Aiman Khan

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q, Concentrated Ownership, Tax Avoidance, Non- Financial Sector, Fixed Effect</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5338902</p>	<p><i>Present study aims to investigate dependency of business performance on concentrated ownership structure. This study has selected non-financial sector of Pakistan for measuring relationship of performance predictors and concentrated ownership structure. Relationship between concentrated ownership structure and performance is measured directly and also with moderation of tax avoidance. Sample of study is collected from 50 non-financial companies out of more than 450 companies listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange. Period of data collection is 6 years starting from 2015 to 2020. Results of study are based panel regression techniques Fixed Effect & Random Effect models and other pre-estimation and post-estimation techniques including descriptive statistics, unit root, correlation analysis and Hausman test. It is found that concentrated ownership significantly influence performance of business positively while tax avoidance moderates this relationship negatively for accounting measures of performance ROA & ROE and no moderating influence is found for market measure of performance Tobin's Q.</i></p>

Introduction

Ownership structure is one of the most important features of the modern companies. This is why an appropriate ownership structure is needed to support the smooth running of company in the market (Zhang & Kyaw, 2017). The structure of ownership in Pakistani companies is highly concentrated. In developing country like Pakistan, the concentrated owners are about 55.20%. This implies that families directly and indirectly are the owners of the companies up to this extent. This paves the way to study the ownership concentration and the ratio of owners in Pakistan (Afgan et al., 2016).

There are different aspects of the ownership concentration though the institutional, managerial, government, family and foreign ownership. There has been a lot of evidence in history of corporate governance that tax avoidance has been used as a legal way for evasion of tax liabilities. The imperfections in the tax laws are due to tax evasion and tax avoidance (Wenman, 2018). There are different dimensions and elements that can affect the tax avoidance practices of the firms; political connections, size of the firm, debts and liabilities, administrative issues, investor's behaviors, management persons, decision makers and the environmental issues. Sometimes, these factors are said to have a large impact on the tax avoidance and sometimes this can have minor and precise effect (Cai, 2015).

Impact of centered ownership was studied on Turkish firms' performance and established the important role of agency conflict (Mandacı & Gumus 2010). Evidences of effect of ownership structure of Spanish companies which includes both privately owned as well as state owned companies on effective tax rate determinants were presented (Rodriguez et al., 2016). Pakistan is one of the developing countries and mostly follows the concentrated ownership structure in public sector companies while here the role of tax avoidance is more likely to be upheld that present study determine in Pakistani non-financial companies.

1. Literature Review

Concentrated ownership has an inverse relationship with the performance of a company. Principal of Cost Effectiveness suggest that large shareholder will be motivated to govern management and maximize the enterprise value as compared to small shareholders. Moreover, concentrated ownership motivates large shareholder to secure their interest on the cost of small shareholders (Madhani, 2016).

Concentrated ownerships give more power to the small number of shareholders, which translate into decrease of board of director's control. This will ultimately reduce firm's reliance on corporate governance practices (Florakis, Kanas, & Kostakis, 2015).

The other effect is Expropriation Effect. In concentrated ownership firms, there are shareholders with high ownership and shareholders with low ownership. High ownership shareholders have power which they can use

to exploit the shareholders with low ownerships in terms of dividend payments to them or transfer of the profits to other units in the firm. This creates an expropriation chance of small shareholders. In this way financial market will suffer (Wahba, 2013).

Concentration of ownership has always been affecting the performance by one way or other. Major shareholders try to control the management and impose their own policies that are usually not liked by the management and it makes independent decision-making more compromised. However, performance of business adversely affected. In cases where there is diversity in ownership and the concentration of one dominant group is low, managers are independent in their decisions and shareholders are not influenced by one specific group (Yasser & Mamoon, 2017).

A study conducted on Jordanian companies revealed that the concentration of ownership is inversely related to the performance of the firms (Mohammed, 2018). In another study, it is evidenced that higher is the concentration of ownership, higher are the chances that owners will pursue personal benefits hence affecting the firm's performance. However, when the ownership concentration is low, agency costs are high and thus the performance will be affected. The performance of Czech firms was maximized in presence of a controlling owner (Machek & Kubíček, 2018). Another study conducted to examine the effects of concentration of the ownership on performance of the Dutch Firms. Results have revealed that ownership concentration is directly linked to the performance and the relationship is quadratic with the firm performance (Boerkamp, 2016).

Another study has examined the association of concentration of ownership with the performance of the European firms. The companies were divided as western and eastern companies. Results showed that for western companies, ownership concentration is directly related to the corporate performance of the firms. For eastern companies, it is not true (Horobet et al., 2019).

Another study conducted in China discussed ownership concentration in institutional ownership and state ownership perspective. The results showed that institutional ownership and performance of the companies are positively related. The concentration of ownership and performance of the firms have no significant relationship (Zhang & Kyaw, 2017).

On the other hand, the relationship of concentration of ownership and tax avoidance is not linear: non-linear. When entrenchment effect is present, a situation in which managerial level has power which they can use to make decision in their own favor, the tax avoidance and concentration of ownership is directly related. This occurs only at low levels. A positive association is also present between tax avoidance and pyramidal ownership structure of the firm (Richardson et al., 2016).

Corporate tax avoidance can be practiced by foreign and government owned firms, this interpretation is based upon cost and benefit analysis of tax avoidance. Value of the company is reduced and price of agency is increased due to the tax avoidance behavior. Relationship between firm performance and tax avoidance can be moderated through introducing transparency of information (Chen et al., 2014).

Some of the tax reductions are legal and cannot be challenged while some falls in a gray area and are ambiguous. The main interest of the shareholders is to maximize their wealth. They do not have or have least interest in the government funding's and the revenues that governments can have through tax payments. If through legal and proper channel, the tax avoidance strategy is successfully implemented then there is a visible increase in shareholder's wealth and decrease in the governmental and fiscal revenues (Garside, 2016).

Companies also have to manage the costs that are related to the tax avoidance activities itself. These costs can be incurred on the tax planning, tax compliance and non-compliance and the non-tax costs. There has been a very complex calculus related to the costs and benefits of the tax avoidance which if not fully understood can have serious negative consequences for the value of the firm (Lee et al., 2015).

In a research study six manufacturing companies from Indonesian stock exchange were examined to study the effect of tax avoidance on performance. Results have shown that tax avoidance has a significant impact on the financial performance of the firms (Ratnawati et al., 2018). Some other researchers have shown the same results that tax avoidance have a significant but negative impact on financial performance or firm value (Santa & Regende, 2016). Some researchers propose that if the tax avoidance is prevalent in firms, then the agency costs may increase resulting in lower firm performance (Chen et al., 2014). There is also found a significant, indirect but positive association between tax avoidance and market value of the firm (Zhang et al., 2016).

2. Data and Methodology

The main objective of this study is to analyze the impact of concentrated ownership structure on firm performance with moderating role of tax avoidance in presence of controlling role of size and leverage of company.

Table 1: Description of Variables

Variable	Definition	Measurement
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Dependent Variable		
ROA	Return on Assets	Net Income/ Average of Total Assets
ROE	Return on Equity	Net Income/ Share Holder's Equity
Tobin's Q	Tobin's Q	Tobin's Q = MVE+D/TA
Independent Variables		
Concentrated Ownership	Ownership Top five shareholders (%)	Fraction of shares owned by the top five owners
Moderating Variable		
TA	Tax Avoidance	Cash Tax Paid/ Earning Before Tax (EBT)
Control Variables		
S	Size	Natural Log of Total Asset
L	Leverage	Debt /Equity

2.1 Description of Variables

Return on Assets

Return on assets is strong measure or proxy for measuring the financial development of the firms (Shabbir, 2018). Higher the return on assets better is performance of the firm (Warrad, 2015).

Return on Equity

When the net income of the firm is divided by the shareholder's equity, it is known as return on equity. It explains how the firm uses owners' equity of the company to create profits (Kijewska, 2016).

Tobin's Q

When the market value of the company is divided by the replacement costs of assets, the result is the Tobin's Q ratio. James Tobin hypothesized that the market value of the firms listed on stock exchange must equalize the replacement costs of the assets (Warrad, 2015).

Concentrated Ownership

The ownership concentration refers to the situation where the major number of shares of a company is held by a few shareholders/owners. These majority shareholders can be a family, group of companies, state or any other foreign investor. There are different levels of the shares held by the concentrated owners. They can be 5%, 10% or 20% of the shares. So the concentrated ownership implies the high control of a firm by a specific category of the shareholders or owners (Madhani, 2016).

Tax Avoidance

Tax avoidance in corporate firms is defined as getting advantage for one's own self in order to reduce the payable tax. The corporate tax avoidance is usually considered as legal and is different from tax sheltering that is not considered as legal. Tax avoidance is usually done through different jurisdictions in which the reduced taxes are facilitated. Tax avoidance is measured by dividing the tax paid in cash with the earnings before the tax (EBT) (Gebhart, 2017).

Size of Company

The performance that a firm shows in financial terms is dependent on the size of the firm and size of the firm has been taken as control variable in numerous researches on performance of the firms (Kuncova et al., 2016).

Leverage of Company

Financial leverage is calculated as the ratio of debt and equity. Financial leverage has been a popular control variable to assess the financial performance of the firm (Domnick, 2018).

2.2 Population and Sample Size

There were more than 450 nonfinancial companies listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange in 2020. This study aims to collect the sample of 10 % at least from nonfinancial companies listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange considering all subsectors equally. However a sample of 50 nonfinancial companies is selected. Data is collected for six years starting from 2015 to 2020.

2.3 Data Analysis Procedure

Descriptive statistics is used to check data normality while unit root is applied for data stationary. Correlation analysis is used to elaborate the association between variables. Fixed and Random effect models are used to examine the relationship of performance measures of nonfinancial companies with the ownership structure and concentration in presence of tax avoidance.

1. ; ROA= $\beta_0it + \beta_1(COS)it + \beta_2(L)it + \beta_3(S)it + e$
2. ; ROA= $\beta_0it + \beta_1(COS)it + \beta_2(L)it + \beta_3(S)it + \beta_4(COS \times TA)it + e$
3. ; ROE= $\beta_0it + \beta_1(COS)it + \beta_2(L)it + \beta_3(S)it + e$
4. ; ROE= $\beta_0it + \beta_1(COS)it + \beta_2(L)it + \beta_3(S)it + \beta_4(COS \times TA)it + e$
5. ; Tobin's Q = $\beta_0it + \beta_1(COS)it + \beta_2(L)it + \beta_3(S)it + e$
6. ; Tobin's Q = $\beta_0it + \beta_1(COS)it + \beta_2(L)it + \beta_3(S)it + \beta_4(COS \times TA)it + e$

Here,

Y= Performance of organizations/firms

a- Constant

(β)= Value of the coefficient

e- Error term

Table1:Descriptive Analysis

Variables	Mean	Median	Max	Mini	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Return on Assets	0.089	0.077	0.67	-0.131	0.096	1.558	8.716
Return on Equity	0.207	0.163	4.139	-0.256	0.303	8.048	99.558
TOBIN'S Q	10.886	3.928	345.62	0.094	28.355	8.097	83.707
Concentrated Ownership	0.771	0.839	0.991	0.280	0.226	-0.976	3.317
Tax Avoidance	0.279	0.246	2.369	-0.001	0.238	2.911	22.693
Leverage	2.13	0.998	67.08	-2.747	6.128	7.563	68.936
Size	16.392	16.337	20.257	13.513	1.534	0.301	2.519

Source: Data Analyzed through E-views 9.5 version

Mean value of ROA is 8.9 % and it deviates to 0.096. Maximum return on assets value is 67 % and minimum return on assets were -13.1 % during the period 2015-2020, it reports net losses against assets of the company. Mean value of ROE is 20.7 % and it deviates to 0.303. Maximum return on equity value is 400.13 % (4 times of equity) and minimum return on equity was -25.6 % during the period 2015-2020, it reports net losses against total equity of the company. Mean value of Tobin's Q is 10.88 and it deviates to 28.35. Maximum Tobin's Q value is 345.62 and minimum Tobin's Q value was 0.094 during the period 2015-2020. Mean value of concentrated ownership is 77.1 % and it deviates to 0.226. Maximum concentrated ownership is 99.1 % and minimum concentrated ownership was 28.0 percent during the period 2015-2020. Mean value of tax avoidance (amount of tax paid in one financial year) is Rs. 1,686,425,000 maximum amount of tax paid in one financial year by a company is Rs. 5,455,656,800 and minimum amount of tax paid in one financial year by a company is Zero. Mean value of leverage (debt to equity) is 2.13 and it deviates to 6.128. Maximum leverage (debt to equity) ratio is 67.08 and minimum leverage (debt to equity) ratio is -2.74, a sign of negative equity during the period 2015-2020. Lastly, mean value of size is 16.39 (natural log value) and it deviates to 1.534.

2.4 Unit Root Analysis

In this research unit root test is used to examine the data stationarity, if data is non-stationarity the forecasting cannot be possible.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Result

Variables	At level using Levin, Lin & Chu t*		
	t static at level	P value	Results
ROA	-15.05	0.000	I(0)
ROE	-13.49	0.000	I(0)
Tobin's Q	-15.05	0.000	I(0)
Concentrated Ownership	-89.27	0.000	I(0)
Tax Avoidance	-8.58	0.000	I(0)
Leverage	-15.12	0.000	I(0)
Size	-4.84	0.000	I(0)

Unit root results based on Levin, Lin & Chu t criteria show t static values > 1.96 and significant p value < 0.05. Thus, data series does not contain unit root and it is stationary at level based on auto lag selection Schwarz Info Criteria.

Table 3: Correlation Statistics

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Return on Assets	1.000							
Return on Equity	0.545	1.000						
TOBIN'S Q	0.110	0.054	1.000					
Concentrated Ownership	0.163	0.165	0.106	1.000				
Tax Avoidance	-0.165	-0.160	-0.018	-0.109	1.000			
Moderator	-0.100	-0.111	-0.004	0.125	0.642	1.000		
Leverage	-0.103	0.215	-0.065	0.027	0.056	0.045	1.000	
Size	0.052	0.134	-0.140	0.178	-0.091	-0.039	0.257	1.000

Source: Data analyse through E-views 9.5

Return on assets positively correlates with concentrated ownership and its value is 16.3 percent while it negatively correlates with tax avoidance, its value is 16.5 percent, correlation between return on assets and moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) is negative, its value is 10.0 percent. While correlation between leverage and return on assets is negative its value is 10.3 percent and correlation between return on assets and size is positive its value is 5.2 percent. Return on equity positively correlates with concentrated ownership and its value is 16.5 percent while it negatively correlates with tax avoidance, its value is 16.0 percent, correlation between return on equity and moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) is negative, its value is 11.1 percent. While correlation between leverage and return on equity is positive its value is 21.5 percent and correlation between return on equity and size is negative its value is 14.0 percent.

Tobin's Q positively correlates with concentrated ownership and its value is 10.6 percent while it negatively correlates with tax avoidance, its value is 1.8 percent (no significant relationship), correlation between Tobin's Q and moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) is also insignificant, its value is 0.04 percent. While correlation between leverage and Tobin's Q is negative its value is 6.5 percent and correlation between Tobin's Q and size is negative its value is 14.0 percent.

Table 4: Regression Analysis Fixed Effect (ROA)

Model	Fixed Effect		
Predictors	Coefficient	T value	P value
Concentrated Ownership	0.159	4.872	0.000

Leverage	0.000	-0.245	0.806
Size	-0.030	-2.482	0.014
Constant	0.459	2.300	0.022
Adjusted R ²	0.669		
F-Static (Sig)	12.65(0.000)		
Hausman Test	8.641 (0.034)		

Source: Data analyse through E-views 9.5

Fixed effect model's results posit 66.9 percent change in return on assets because of predictors including concentrated ownership, leverage and size with assumption that something within individual companies may bias the outcomes of panel result however it requires to be controlled. F statics value 12.65 along with Sig. value 0.000 < 0.05 validates model fitness. In beta coefficients, X1 (concentrated ownership) causes .159 units positive change in Y (return on assets) when X1 (concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. While, X3 (size of company) causes .03 units negative change in Y (return on assets) when X3 (size of company) changes by 1 unit. On the other hand, post-estimation Hausman test value is 8.641 along with Sig. value 0.000 < 0.05 it validates fixed effect to interpret the outcomes in panel results.

Table 5: Regression Analysis Fixed Effect (ROA)with Moderator Tax Avoidance

Model	Fixed Effect		
Predictors	Coefficient	T value	P value
Concentrated Ownership	0.107	3.830	0.000
Tax Avoidance	-0.125	-6.633	0.000
Moderator	-0.220	-5.178	0.000
Leverage	0.000	-0.358	0.721
Size	-0.018	-1.783	0.076
Constant	0.379	2.317	0.021
Adjusted R ²	0.779		
F-Static (Sig)	20.55(0.000)		
Hausman Test	23.09 (0.000)		

Source: Data analyse through E-views 9.5

Fixed effect model's results posit 77.9 percent change in return on assets because of predictors including concentrated ownership, tax avoidance, moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) leverage and size with assumption that something within individual companies may bias the outcomes of panel result however it requires to be controlled. F statics value 20.55 along with Sig. value 0.000 < 0.05 validates model fitness. In beta coefficients, X1 (concentrated ownership) causes .107 units positive change in Y (return on assets) when X1 (concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. While, X2 (tax avoidance) causes .125 units negative change in Y (return on assets) when X2 (tax avoidance) changes by 1 unit. On the other hand, X3 moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) causes .220 units negative change in Y (return on assets) when X3 moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. On the other hand, post-estimation Hausman test value is 23.09 along with Sig. value 0.000 < 0.05 it validates fixed effect to interpret the outcomes in panel results.

Table 6: Regression Analysis Fixed Effect (ROE)

Model	Fixed Effect		
Predictors	Coefficient	T value	P value
Concentrated Ownership	0.436	2.993	0.003
Leverage	0.013	3.174	0.002
Size	-0.020	-0.370	0.711
Constant	0.171	0.192	0.848
Adjusted R ²	0.334		
F-Static (Sig)	03.88(0.000)		

Hausman Test 6.421 (0.031)

Source: Data analyse through E-views 9.5

Fixed effect model's results posit 33.4 percent change in return on equity because of predictors including concentrated ownership, leverage and size with assumption that something within individual companies may bias the outcomes of panel result however it requires to be controlled. F statics value 3.88 along with Sig. value $0.000 < 0.05$ validates model fitness. In beta coefficients, X1 (concentrated ownership) causes .436 units positive change in Y (return on equity) when X1 (concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. While, X2 (leverage of company) causes .013 units negative change in Y (return on equity) when X2 (leverage of company) changes by 1 unit. On the other hand, post-estimation Hausman test value is 6.421 along with Sig. value $0.031 < 0.05$ it validates fixed effect to interpret the outcomes in panel results.

Table 7: Regression Analysis Fixed Effect (ROE)with Moderator Tax Avoidance

Model	Fixed Effect		
Predictors	Coefficient	T value	P value
Concentrated Ownership	0.306	2.111	0.036
Tax Avoidance	-0.311	-3.173	0.002
Moderator	-0.527	-2.381	0.018
Leverage	0.013	3.308	0.001
Size	0.010	0.189	0.851
Constant	-0.021	-0.024	0.981
Adjusted R ²	0.396		
F-Static (Sig)	04.63(0.000)		
Hausman Test	11.42 (0.043)		

Source: Data analyse through E-views 9.5

Fixed effect model's results posit 39.6 percent change in return on equity because of predictors including concentrated ownership, tax avoidance, moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) leverage and size with assumption that something within individual companies may bias the outcomes of panel result however it requires to be controlled. F statics value 04.63 along with Sig. value $0.000 < 0.05$ validates model fitness. In beta coefficients, X1 (concentrated ownership) causes .306 units positive change in Y (return on equity) when X1 (concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. While, X2 (tax avoidance) causes .311 units negative change in Y (return on equity) when X2 (tax avoidance) changes by 1 unit. On the other hand, X3 moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) causes .527 units negative change in Y (return on equity) when X3 moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. Here, leverage negatively controls this relationship. On the other hand, post-estimation Hausman test value is 11.42 along with Sig. value $0.000 < 0.05$ it validates fixed effect to interpret the outcomes in panel results.

Table 8: Regression Analysis Fixed Effect (Tobin's Q)

Model	Fixed Effect		
Predictors	Coefficient	T value	P value
Concentrated Ownership	16.905	2.303	0.022
Leverage	-0.131	-0.474	0.636
Size	-2.899	-2.589	0.010
Constant	45.650	2.514	0.013
Adjusted R ²	0.028		
F-Static (Sig)	03.82(0.010)		
Hausman Test	9.854 (0.005)		

Source: Data analyse through E-views 9.5

Fixed effect model's results posit 2.8 percent change in tobin's Q because of predictors including concentrated ownership, leverage and size with assumption that something within individual companies may bias the outcomes of panel result however it requires to be controlled. F statics value 3.82 along with Sig. value $0.000 < 0.05$ validates model fitness. In beta coefficients, X1 (concentrated ownership) causes 16.90 units positive change in Y (tobin's Q)

when X1 (concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. While, X3 (size of company) causes -2.899 units negative change in Y (tobin's Q) when X3 (size of company) changes by 1 unit.

On the other hand, post-estimation Hausman test value is 9.854 along with Sig. value $0.005 < 0.05$ it validates fixed effect to interpret the outcomes in panel results.

Table 9: Regression Analysis Fixed Effect (Tobin's Q)with Moderator Tax Avoidance

Model	Fixed Effect		
Predictors	Coefficient	T value	P value
Concentrated Ownership	11.826	1.96	0.051
Tax Avoidance	-6.490	-0.875	0.383
Moderator	-23.969	-1.431	0.154
Leverage	-0.060	-0.205	0.838
Size	4.610	1.174	0.242
Constant	-66.874	-1.037	0.301
Adjusted R ²	0.606		
F-Static (Sig)	09.51(0.000)		
Hausman Test	7.39 (0.025)		

Source: Data analyse through E-views 9.5

Fixed effect model's results posit 60.6 percent change in tobin's Q because of predictors including concentrated ownership, tax avoidance, moderator (tax avoidance x concentrated ownership) leverage and size with assumption that something within individual companies may bias the outcomes of panel result however it requires to be controlled. F statics value 09.51 along with Sig. value $0.000 < 0.05$ validates model fitness. In beta coefficients, X1 (concentrated ownership) causes 11.82 units positive change in Y (tobin's Q) when X1 (concentrated ownership) changes by 1 unit. While no other predictor causing significant change in tobin's Q.

On the other hand, post-estimation Hausman test value is 7.39 along with Sig. value $0.025 < 0.05$ it validates fixed effect to interpret the outcomes in panel results.

3. Conclusion and Recommendations

The concentration of ownership is said to have an impact on the value of shareholder and their identity. The results of our study also showed the same results that concentrated ownership has a significant positive impact on the performance of the organization. Tax avoidance can be good as well as it can be bad. Reduction in explicit taxes can be stated as tax avoidance and it is broad category of tax management activities which include; tax management, tax planning, tax aggressiveness, tax evasion and tax sheltering. Considering taxes as costs firms can effectively manage and plan to reduce the cost which will yield high profitability by adding to value of shareholders, such an activity is not harmful for the society so tax avoidance is good in this case. On the other hand, firm may involve in processes like tax evasion or tax shelter in which sole desire of firm is to avoid tax such a practice is not considered good on firm's end as well as for society. A firm in which concentrated ownership structure exist tax avoidance is use by the majority shareholders in such a way that it structures incentives in order to increase the value of firm (Huseynov&Klamm, 2012). Our results have shown that the tax avoidance moderates the relationship of concentration of ownership with performance of firm.

This study will help the practitioners and academicians to relate the concentration of ownership and the performance of the organizations. Practitioners and policy makers can get help from this study to go into some direction and making an objective assessment. The corporate governance practices and the tax avoidance are responsible for the agency problems as well as reducing the agency problems. Researchers have been putting a lot of efforts for making this relationship conclusive. This study is aligned with the convergence-of-interest hypothesis that was first proposed by Jensen &Meckling in 1976. Managers and practitioners can learn that the alignment of interests of principals and agents can be done in light of this study. There are some benefits of control that can help the practitioners to assess the ratios of the owners. This study will help the firms to assess the size of the firm and the impact of the ownership concentration on the performance. The owners that have a higher level of ownership ratio in Pakistan have some important implications in the corporate governance sector. If the ownership concentration is high, it can have an impact on the law making and policy designs that in turn can mitigate agency costs. Mitigation of agency costs will increase the performance of the organization.

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Author Information

Sabah Younus

Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, National university of Modern Language, Multan – Pakistan

M.Wasim Rana

Instructor, Department of Management Sciences, Govt. Vocational Training Institute, Burewala – Pakistan

Ume Aiman Khan

MBA Student, at National University of Modern
Language, Multan- Pakistan
